

An Analysis and Study of Mahatma Gandhi and his Education Thoughts

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As indicated by him a genuine, fair, and ethically solid unskilled individual is much better than an ethically degenerate profoundly taught person. By the by, he was additionally of the assessment that education is fundamental for improvement and development, yet the intelligence procured by education must be utilized in the development of the country and welfare of individual compatriots.

(Fig. 1 Mahtma Gandhi)

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with Mahatma Gandhi and his contribution and educational thoughts. Gandhi was not only a man, he is a thought. A thought which can never be outdated to get denied. With the increasing terrorism and violence in the world, he is becoming more significant to observe and learn. A thought which was meant for all. He was a strong supporter of education. Gandhian Educational thoughts are important for improvement and giving arrangements of the present issues like joblessness, destitution, defilement and numerous others.

KEYWORDS: Mahatma Gandhi, educational, thoughts, contribution etc.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Education system proposed by Mahatma Gandhi is called as "Basic Education". He predominantly goes for the education in first language and requested action focused education to make the youngsters gifted and autonomous. Gandhiji needed to build little; independent networks with its optimal residents being all enterprising, self-regarding and liberal people living in a little co-employable and network. He wanted that some neighborhood art ought to be made as mode of education for youngsters with the goal that they build up their psyche, body and soul in an amicable manner and furthermore address the issues of their future life. Mahatma Gandhi had faith in the inside and out advancement of an individual by method for instructing him on various levels. According to him, an individual is really taught when he can draw out the best from inside. He upheld that lone procuring proficiency does not mean being taught. Education includes much more. He worried on good education of a man more than the scholarly education.

2. Review of Literature:

Education, similar to family, marriage, religion, law and legislative issues is one of the significant foundations of society which assume vital job in keeping up and creating social system (Tandon, 2016). Gandhiji's commitment to education is interesting in this feeling he made the principal endeavor to build up an indigenous plan of education in British India. With the approach of British provincial guideline in India, an outsider system of supreme education was presented which was in inconsistency with the deep rooted, extraordinary and comprehensive all encompassing educational system of India. It has not just made hopeless harm Indian education system over the long haul, yet in addition made quantities of a wide range of contrasts, class-cognizance, consistently expanding want for western materialistic way of life, and so on. A large portion of Gandhiji's significant works on education have been arranged and altered by Bharatan Kumarappa in two books, Basic Education (1951) and Towards New Education (1953). These compositions are for the most part incidental comprising of letters, discourses, separates from books, and soon, however together they might be taken to establish an intelligible way of thinking of education as per Gandhiji. His way of thinking of education is an agreeable mixing of Idealism, Naturalism and Pragmatism. Vision is the base of Gandhiji's way of thinking though Naturalism and Pragmatism are the partners in making an interpretation of that way of thinking into training. Along these lines he is

known as down to earth dreamer. His country was "education forever, education through life, and education all through life." This meaning of Mahatma Gandhi would include everything that can be imagined under education. In the present paper an endeavor has been made to examine about the Gandhi's Educational idea which were affected by his way of thinking of life. Mahatma Gandhi is a soul of significant astuteness and enamoring modesty, equipped with just an iron will and resolute purpose and a delicate man who went up against the severity of military quality with the poise of a straightforward individual. He put stock in God certainly. As per him, however people have various bodies, yet a similar soul overruns within each one of us. So, Gandhiji experienced and acknowledged Unity in Diversity. His way of thinking of life has four components to be specific (1) Truth, (2) Non-Violence (3) Fearlessness and (4) Satyagraha (Saxena, 2003). Gandhiji's way of thinking to life depends on the way of thinking of Idealism. He upheld the goals of truth, peacefulness and virtues to accomplish a definitive truth of self-acknowledgment. He is tyke as per his tendency and he turns into a logical thinker when he promotes learning by doing and learning by understanding. All these lead to a reconciliation, so basic to successful education and improvement of the absolute character. (Saxena, 2003). Gandhiji was not a scholarly rationalist but rather based on his own encounters he is one of those savants who had confidence in benevolence. In his way of thinking there is extremely clear indication of his adoration for individual and national opportunity. He had a multidimensional character with clear vision and distinct way to deal with issues which were available in the nation. Gandhiji reasoning of peacefulness has extraordinary significance in current situation. As per him peacefulness does not mean quiet accommodation to the desire of the scalawag. It is the spirit power or truth power. (Vijayalakshmi, 2016). The reason for his Satyagrah is to battle against foul play. Satyagrah ought to have the ethical face to accomplish change of heart without anyone else enduring of the adherence of truth and peacefulness. Such way of thinking of life helped him in building up his way of thinking of Education which can be the genuine wellspring of motivation for the present system of education.

3. Mahatma Gandhi and his educational thoughts:

Gandhiji's Basic Education was the handy exemplification of his way of thinking of education. His essential education takes up the difficult errand of setting up the youthful students to turn out to be ethically solid, separately independents, socially useful, financially gainful and dependable future natives which can demonstrate accommodating in taking care of the issue of joblessness by making youth independently employed by giving them ability preparing. Gandhiji accepted that education ought to build up every one of the limits of the youngster so he turns into a total person. Along these lines, completely and amicably created character can understand a definitive point of life which is Truth or God. Gandhiji has himself clarified - "By education I mean all-round drawing out of the best in youngster's and man's body, brain and soul. Proficiency is neither the start nor the part of the bargain. This is just a methods through which man or lady can be instructed." His Basic Principles of Education incorporates:-

1. From seven to fourteen years of age, education of each child should be free, compulsory and universal.
2. The medium of instruction should be mother-tongue.

3. Mere literacy cannot be equated with education. Education should employ some craft as a medium of education so that the child gains economic self-reliance for his life.
4. Education should develop human values in the child.
5. Education should create useful, responsible and dynamic citizens. By education all the hidden powers of child should develop according to the community of which he is an integral part.
6. Education should achieve the harmonious development of child's body, mind, heart and soul.
7. All education should be imparted through some productive craft or industry and a useful correlation should be established with that industry. The industry should be such that the child is able to achieve gainful work experience through practical work.
8. Education should be made self-supporting through some productive work. Education should lead to economic independence and self-reliance for livelihood.

Hence, in Gandhiji's educational thoughts the advancement of the character of kid could really compare to minor proficiency or learning of various subjects. As it were he put stock in life-focused just as youngster focused education. Other than learning of three R's Reading, Writing and Arithmetic in school, he demanded advancement of these H's Hand, Heart and Head. In this way, the point of Education ought to be of building up the coordinated character of the child. Gandhiji was having lucidity in the possibility that one of the fundamental standards of education is that work and information should never be isolated. Division of gaining from work brings about social shameful acts. In powerful social orders, education needs to outfit people with the aptitudes and dispositions essential for them to adjust to evolving conditions, and for valuable support in the assignment of social change. This can demonstrate accommodating in taking care of the issues of dissatisfaction, sadness, nervousness and sentiment of ending it all among youth. According to Gandhiji through education a youngster must most likely get familiar with a gainful art to meet his future needs of life by receiving some industry or business. Thus, he pushed education for confidence and ability to acquire one's work as the fundamental point of education. By this point he meant to make the kid a worker yet wanted that every youngster ought to acquire while occupied with learning and increase some learning as he is occupied with procuring. He pushed that together with professional education social progression ought to likewise be accomplished. The two parts of improvement ought to go together side by side. Gandhiji demanded that education ought to build up all parts of distinction amicably. He additionally accepted that one of the basic points of education is the ethical advancement or character improvement. Gandhiji wishes that each tyke ought to develop into a perfect person by acknowledging Godliness in his self. Gandhiji himself composes. "To build up oneself is to construct character and to set up the self for complete acknowledgment and acknowledgment of Godliness. Gandhiji's 'Fundamental Education' was occupation focused, esteem based and mass arranged. Here note that these are as yet the significant prerequisites of education in our nation. In his plan of education, information must be identified with movement and down to earth encounters. Along these lines

his educational program is action focused. Its point is to set up the youngster for commonsense work, direct explores and do examine with the goal that he can create himself physically, rationally and profoundly and become a valuable individual from society. In this action focused educational plan, Gandhiji included Mother-tongue, Basic Craft, Arithmetic, Sociology, General Science, Art, Music and other like subjects. He further upheld that educational program for young men and young ladies from classes 1 to 5 ought to be the equivalent. After that young men ought to be trained some Craft and young ladies should concentrate Home-Science. It ought to be noticed that Gandhiji's plan of Basic Education is restricted to essential and junior stages only. Gandhiji likewise demanded that his plan for essential education would incorporate "the basic standards of sanitation, cleanliness, nourishment," other than "necessary physical preparing through melodic drill. Gandhiji contends that his plan would make understudies solid, certain and valuable to their folks and their nation. Gandhiji includes that his system would prompt shared amicability since it would be the equivalent for all; it would this be "reasonable religion, the religion of self help". Gandhiji objected repetition learning educational strategies and thought about it as imperfect and accentuated to make artworks and employments as methods for education. He wanted that some neighborhood art ought to be made as mechanism of education for youngsters with the goal that they build up their body, psyche and soul in an agreeable manner and furthermore meet the closures needs to their future life. Along these lines, Gandhiji's technique for instructing was in this way, not quite the same as the present one. He emphasized the importance of the following principles in his method of teaching-

1. To achieve mental development, training of senses and parts of the body should be given.
2. Reading should precede the teaching of writing.
3. More opportunities should be given for learning by doing.
4. Encouragement should be given to learning by experience.

5. Correlation should be established in the teaching methods and learning experiences.

4. References:

- [1] Shah, P.K. (2017), "Gandhiji's views on Basic Education and its Relevance", Pune Research an International Journal in English, Vol.3, Issue4.
- [2] Vijaylakshmi, N. and others (2016), "Relevance of Gandhian Philosophy in the 21st century", International Journal of Research in Engineering, I T and Social Science, Vol. 6, Issue1.
- [3] Saxena, S. (2003), "Principles of Education", Meerat, Surya Publication. Tandan, S. (2016), "Teachers in the Making", New Delhi, Classical Publishing Company. Pillai, "Gandhi's concept on Education and Its Relevance in the Present Day" Retrieved from <http://www.iop.or.jp> > Documents > Pillai.
- [4] *Mahatma Gandhi (2005)*. All Men Are Brothers. *Bloomsbury Academic*. p. 22. ISBN 978-0-8264-1739-8.
- [5] *Rahul Sagar (2015)*. *David M. Malone; et al. (eds.)*. The Oxford Handbook of Indian Foreign Policy. *Oxford University Press*. pp. 71-73. ISBN 978-0-19-106118-9.
- [6] *Rahul Sagar (2015)*. *David M. Malone; et al. (eds.)*. The Oxford Handbook of Indian Foreign Policy. *Oxford University Press*. p. 70. ISBN 978-0-19-106118-9.
- [7] *Gene Sharp (1960)*. Gandhi Wields the Weapon of Moral Power: Three Case Histories. *Navajivan*. p. 4.
- [8] *Dennis Dalton (2012)*. Mahatma Gandhi: Nonviolent Power in Action. *Columbia University Press*. pp. 30-32. ISBN 978-0-231-15959-3.
- [9] *William Borman (1986)*. Gandhi and Non-Violence. *State University of New York Press*. pp. 26-34. ISBN 978-0-88706-331-2.
- [10] *Indira Carr (2012)*. *Stuart Brown; et al. (eds.)*. Biographical Dictionary of Twentieth-Century Philosophers. *Routledge*. p. 264. ISBN 978-1-134-92796-8.